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agrigatemagazine@gmail.com

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GLOBALISATION AND AGRICULTURE

Adarsh S.^{1*}, Ameena M.², Shalini Pillai P.³

¹Research Scholar, ²Professor (Agronomy), ³ Professor (Agronomy) and Head,

^{1,2,3}Department of Agronomy, College of Agriculture, Vellayani,

Kerala Agricultural University, Kerala, India

*Corresponding Author Email ID: sssadarshsss@gmail.com

Introduction

Globalisation, also known as mundialisation, is a commonly used term that describes the processes of international integration resulting from the growing interconnectedness of people and the exchange of worldviews, goods, ideas, and various cultural elements. Its primary objective is to break down barriers, particularly in trade. Interestingly, globalisation has a more extended history than one might initially think. It involves the removal of impediments to work, communication, and the sharing of cultures. The underlying theory behind globalisation posits that fostering worldwide openness will enhance the prosperity of all nations. It can be referred to as improving the connectivity and interdependence of global markets and businesses. In essence, globalisation represents the framework for interaction among nations worldwide, aimed at fostering the global economy. It signifies the integration of economies and societies across the globe. Over the past two decades, globalisation has rapidly accelerated. This surge can be attributed primarily to advancements in telecommunications infrastructure and the ascent of the internet. Generally, as economies become more intertwined, they offer increased opportunities and face heightened competition. Consequently, as globalisation becomes a more prevalent aspect of the global economy, influential proponents and opponents of globalisation have emerged. Advocates for globalisation argue that it brings forth numerous opportunities for nearly everyone, asserting that increased competition is beneficial as it enhances the efficiency of

production agents. The two most prominent organisations supporting globalisation are the World Trade Organization and the World Economic Forum. Conversely, opponents of globalisation contend that certain groups lacking resources may struggle to cope with the intensified competitive pressures of greater economic integration. Notable anti-globalisation organisations include environmental groups like Friends of the Earth and Greenpeace, international aid organisations such as Oxfam, third-world government bodies like the G-77, and business associations and labour unions whose competitiveness is threatened by globalisation, such as the U.S. textiles sector and the European farm lobby, as well as the trade union movements in Australia and the United States (Leichenko and O'Brien, 2008).

Effects of Globalization

According to economists, globalisation and integration are associated with numerous global developments, and the transformative effects of globalisation are readily identifiable.

1. **Enhancement of International Trade:** Globalization has significantly expanded the number of countries where products can be bought and sold.
2. **Technological Advancements:** In response to the imperative of global competitiveness, governments have upgraded their technological capabilities.
3. **Augmented Influence of Multinational Corporations:** Multinational companies, with their headquarters often in their country of origin, have subsidiaries across different nations. For instance, a Japanese car company may have branches in various countries, with production decisions typically made by these subsidiaries. Penetrating local markets empowers these subsidiaries to boost production and profits. The rise of multinational corporations began after World War II, and their presence in host countries has grown as a result of globalisation.
4. **Strengthened Roles of the WTO, IMF, and WB:** Globalization has contributed to the increased power and influence of international institutions such as the World Trade Organization (WTO), International Monetary Fund (IMF), and World Bank (WB), according to experts.
5. **Heightened Mobility of Human Resources Across Borders:** Globalization enables countries to tap into the labour force of nations with cost-effective labour. For instance, countries like Taiwan, South Korea, and Malaysia facing labour shortages offer opportunities for labour-exporting countries like the Philippines to provide their workforce for employment.

6. Expanded Outsourcing of Business Functions to Foreign Countries: Nations like China, India, and the Philippines have greatly benefited from the trend of global business outsourcing. U.S. and European global companies leverage the cost-effective labour and highly skilled workers available in countries like India and the Philippines.

7. Influence of Civil Society: An essential facet of globalisation is the global civil society's growing influence and broader reach, often represented by non-governmental organisations (NGOs). These are institutions established and operated by citizens and encompass various societal aspects, including family. In globalisation, global civil society comprises organisations advocating for specific issues or causes, such as women's rights or environmental preservation. These organisations aim to shape policies for the collective good rather than opposing government policies. Both governments and NGOs share the common goal of serving the people. Globalisation has further amplified the influence of NGOs, particularly in critical areas like human rights, the environment, children's welfare, and workers' rights. Simultaneously, multinational corporations have seen their power grow.

World Trade Organization (WTO)

The WTO is the global international body responsible for regulating trade between nations. At its core, the WTO operates through agreements collectively negotiated and ratified by most of the world's trading nations through their parliamentary processes. Its fundamental aim is to facilitate the activities of producers of goods and services, exporters, and importers. The primary mission of the World Trade Organization, or WTO, is to promote open trade to the advantage of all participants. It serves as a platform for negotiating agreements to reduce barriers to international trade, fostering equitable conditions for all stakeholders, thereby promoting economic growth and development. Moreover, the WTO furnishes the legal and institutional framework necessary for enforcing and overseeing these accords and resolving disputes arising from their interpretation and application. The current collection of trade agreements under the purview of the WTO encompasses 16 distinct multilateral contracts (to which all WTO members are signatories) and two distinct plurilateral agreements (entered into by select WTO members). Over the past six decades, the WTO, established in 1995, and its precursor, the GATT, have played pivotal roles in forging a robust and prosperous global trading system, thus contributing to unparalleled worldwide economic expansion. Currently, the WTO counts 155 member

nations, with 117 classified as developing countries or separate customs territories. The WTO's activities are facilitated by a Secretariat comprised of around 700 personnel, led by the WTO Director-General, and headquartered in Geneva, Switzerland. The Secretariat operates with an annual budget of approximately \$180 million. English, French, and Spanish serve as the three official languages of the WTO. Decisions within the WTO are typically reached by consensus among its entire membership. The supreme governing body is the Ministerial Conference, convened roughly every two years, while the General Council oversees the organisation's functions between Ministerial Conferences. Both of these entities include representation from all member nations. Specialised subsidiary bodies such as Councils, Committees, and Subcommittees, composed of all member nations, administer and supervise the implementation of the various WTO agreements by its members. The main activities of WTO include:

- Engaging in negotiations aimed at reducing or eliminating barriers to trade, such as import tariffs and other impediments to trade, and establishing regulations governing international trade conduct (e.g., addressing issues like antidumping practices, subsidies, product standards, and more)
- Overseeing and ensuring the implementation of the agreed-upon rules for trade in goods, services, and intellectual property rights related to trade
- Monitoring and assessing the trade policies of member nations while promoting transparency in regional and bilateral trade agreements
- Resolving disputes among member countries concerning the interpretation and application of the agreements
- Developing the capabilities of government officials in developing countries in matters related to international trade
- Facilitating the accession process for approximately 30 countries seeking membership in the organisation
- Conducting economic research and collecting and disseminating trade-related data to support the WTO's primary functions
- Educating and informing the public about the WTO, its mission, and its activities.

The WTO's foundational and guiding principles focus on pursuing open borders, ensuring the most favoured nation code and non-discriminatory treatment among its members, and a commitment to transparent conduct in its operations. The opening of national markets to

international trade, with exceptions or flexibilities as needed, is anticipated to promote sustainable development, improve the well-being of populations, alleviate poverty, and foster global peace and stability (Hufbauer and Cimino-Isaacs, 2015).

General Agreement on Tariffs and Trade (GATT)

GATT is a multinational accord governing global trade. As outlined in its preamble, its stated objective is substantially reducing tariffs and other trade barriers and eliminating preferences through reciprocal and mutually advantageous means. GATT emerged during the United Nations Conference on Trade and Employment and came into being after negotiations for establishing the International Trade Organization (ITO) proved unsuccessful. GATT was initially signed in 1947 and remained in effect until 1993, when it was succeeded by forming the World Trade Organization (WTO) in 1995. The original GATT text (GATT 1947) continues to be in force under the WTO framework, albeit subject to the amendments of GATT 1994. In 1993, GATT underwent an update (GATT 1994) that introduced new obligations for its signatories, with one of the most significant changes being the establishment of the WTO. The WTO was established on January 1, 1995, with the 75 existing GATT members and the European Communities becoming its founding members. Over the following two years, the remaining 52 GATT members joined the WTO, the last being Congo in 1997. Since the inception of the WTO, 21 new members, not originally part of GATT, have joined, and 29 others are currently negotiating their membership. The WTO comprises 155 member countries, including Montenegro and Samoa, which became new members in 2012. Syria and the former Socialist Federal Republic of Yugoslavia (SFR Yugoslavia) have not rejoined the WTO. Since Yugoslavia underwent changes, becoming Serbia and Montenegro and later splitting into two entities, its application is considered new (non-GATT). The WTO's General Council established a working party in 2010 to assess Syria's request for WTO membership. The original contracting parties of GATT concluded their official agreement under the "GATT 1947" terms on December 31, 1995. Serbia and Montenegro are currently in the decision phase of negotiations and are anticipated to become the WTO's newest members shortly. While GATT primarily consisted of agreed-upon rules among nations, the WTO is an institutional body. The WTO expanded its purview beyond the goods trade to encompass marketing within the service sector and intellectual property rights. Although designed to facilitate multilateral agreements, several rounds of GATT negotiations,

such as the Tokyo Round, led to the creation of plurilateral agreements, resulting in selective trading and some fragmentation among member nations. Essentially, WTO arrangements generally function as a multilateral agreement settlement mechanism derived from GATT (Finalyson and Zacher, 1981).

Consequences of Globalization on Indian Agriculture

A) Positive Consequences (Shinde, 2015)

Availability of modern Agro- technologies

New breeds of high-yield crops and contemporary agrotechnologies, including pesticides, herbicides, and fertilisers, enhanced food production. These technologies included up-to-date irrigation projects, herbicides, synthetic nitrogen fertiliser, and improved crop types created using the then-current conventional scientific techniques. They were using HYVs, such as the semi-dwarf rice variety IR8. With sufficient irrigation, herbicides, and fertilisers, HYVs significantly outperformed traditional cultivars.

Rise in production and productivity

The country's production of food grains grew significantly due to the implementation HYV technology. Wheat was produced from 8.8 million tonnes in 1965–1966 to 184 million tonnes in 1991–1992. Other food grains now have more food with greater efficiency. Between 1965–1966 and 1989–1990, it was 71% for cereals, 104% for wheat, and 52% for paddy. Although food grain output has expanded significantly, coarse cereals, pulses, and a few cash crops have not benefited from the green revolution. In other words, not all crops have benefited equally from the green course.

Growth of National Income

Farmers' agricultural output has increased due to receiving the global market for their products. The farm product was grown with innovative technologies, seeds, farming methods, etc. From a financial perspective, the agriculture sector's contribution to the economy has increased to 14.2% of GDP (2010–11).

New areas of employment

When exporting agricultural goods, it is required to classify the products, standardise their processing, bundle them, etc. As a result, the agro-allied industries have generated employment in several sectors, including cold storage, packing, exporting, standardising, and processing. Agriculture-dependent enterprises are being stored, which has increased engagement.

The largest unorganised sector of the Indian economy, accounting for more than 90% of the disorganised labour force, is agriculture. 52.1% of the workforce is employed in agriculture.

Agriculture as a prime moving force

According to the presumption, a 1% rise in agricultural growth results in a 0.5% increase in industrial output and a 0.7% increase in India's national revenue. The farm sector in India is expanding quickly, especially following LPG. As a result, the Indian government declared agriculture the main driver of the country's economy in 2002.

Rise in the share of trade

The WTO's rules ensure that all nations have equal possibilities, which has led to a growth in agricultural exports. In the five years following the onset of globalisation, from 1990 to 1999, India's percentage of exports (goods and services) increased from 0.54% to 0.67%, according to figures published by the World Bank. The same era saw a 103% increase in Indian exports.

Growth of Agro exports

The prices of agricultural goods are higher in the international market than in the Indian market. If the developed countries reduce grants, they have to increase costs. So, there will be an increase in the exports in the Indian market, and if the prices grow, there will be profit. Agricultural products account for 10.23% of the total export income of the economy, while agrarian imports account for just 2.74% of the total imports.

Reduction in poverty

Furthermore, globalisation is frequently cited as widening the gap between the rich and the poor, but this depends on how one defines poverty. India's top priority is eradicating poverty, which is worse than dying. If India makes an effort, globalisation can help India achieve this goal. Additionally, the proportion of impoverished individuals has steadily declined, from 36 per cent in 1993–1994 to 21.9 per cent in 2011–12.

B) Negative Consequences (O'Brien *et al.*, 2004)

Vicious debt trap and farmers' suicides

It is necessary to investigate each contributing factor to the current agricultural sector crisis and evaluate the impact of liberalisation measures. For instance, the state of Andhra Pradesh forged the first-ever state-level deal with the World Bank, which included an 830-million-dollar loan in exchange for several changes to the state's economy and administration. It

has enthusiastically and zealously adopted the World Bank's liberalisation programmes, and as a result, the state's rate of farmer suicides has increased. According to the National Sample Survey Organisation (NSSO) Report 2005, one in two farm households is in debt, with just 10% of that debt being used for non-production activities.

Migration of labours

The lack of post-harvest storage facilities has led to a significant loss of produce and income for Indian farmers, who are already crippled by low production. It is only because of the low import tariffs brought forth by liberalised import duties, which was a shocker. The domestic farmer could not compete in the global market, which led to a shift in employment from agriculture to other industrial pursuits.

Lower-income of rural farmers

According to Nobel Prize-winning economist Joseph Stiglitz, Trade agreements now forbid most subsidies except agricultural goods. This depresses the incomes of those farmers in developing countries who do not get grants. And since 70 per cent of those in the developing countries depend directly or indirectly on agriculture, the incomes of the developing countries are depressed. But by whatever standard one uses, today's international trading regime is unfair to developing countries. He also pointed out that the average European cow gets a subsidy of \$ 2 a day (the World Bank measure of poverty); more than half the people in the developing world live on less than that. It appears it is better to be a cow in Europe than a poor person in a developing country.

Lessening international competitiveness

In India, 60% of the population depends on agriculture. This pressure on agriculture is increasing daily because of the increasing population. Because of marginal land holding, the production cost of Indian farmers is higher, and the quality and standardisation of agro-produce are much neglected. On the contrary, before the WTO reduced grants, developed countries had distributed gifts on a large scale. They had grown the amount of the large-scale contributions in agriculture from 1988-1994. So, they need to avoid many difficulties if there is a reduction in subsidies. On this background, the farmers need to be able to compete in the international market.

Abnormal hike in Fertilizers and Pesticide prices

Indian farmers were encouraged to switch from growing traditional crops to export-oriented "cash crops" like tobacco, cotton, and chilli after the rupee was devalued by 25% shortly after globalisation and Indian crops became very affordable and appealing on the international market. These demand much more insecticides, fertilisers, and water than conventional crops. The cost of pesticides and fertiliser automatically increased by 300%.

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